

A corpus-based study of word-formation creativity in Facebook Philippine English

Nimfa G. Dimaculangan¹, Michelle B. Sarmiento²

¹College of Teacher Education, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Santa Cruz (Main) Campus, Santa Cruz, Philippines

²College of Teacher Education, Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo City, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 4, 2022

Revised Oct 24, 2023

Accepted Nov 2, 2023

Keywords:

Computer-mediated communication

English as a second language

Facebook Philippine English

Internet English

Word-formation creativity

ABSTRACT

This paper is a study of English as a second language (ESL) teachers' and students' newly coined Facebook (FB) lexical items and expressions. It presents sample FB Philippine English (PhilE) words found in ESL teachers' and students' FB posts and messages and the formation mechanisms evident in the lexical items. The lexical items are culled from the researchers-built 50,000-word corpus of FB and FB Messenger conversations posted and sent by the mentioned texts' contributors from the last quarter of 2016 to 2022. The PhilE neologisms are identified from their surrounding English lexical items and analyzed based on a proposed framework for PhilE word-formation processes, and ESL Englishes well-motivated innovations and criteria in standardizing its usages. Data analysis reveals over a hundred PhilE lexical items that are coined through the analytical frameworks used with the present paper's additional proposed processes for FB lexical formation, hypocoristic extension, and anagrammatic transposition or backward spelling. The lexical items, in general, are colloquial, marking the informality of the FB PhilE register, although written in English. In terms of lexicon, it is advanced that FB English in the country is a variety of Internet PhilE, which should be taught in Sociolinguistics and ESL classrooms.

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Corresponding Author:

Nimfa G. Dimaculangan

College of Teacher Education, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Santa Cruz (Main) Campus

Santa Cruz, Laguna, Philippines

Email: nimfadimaculangan@lspu.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

English, the language of globalization, has been at the forefront of digitalization. Digitalization quickens the globalization of the mother English, British English (BrE), which has produced children Englishes. Emerging Englishes within the World Englishes paradigm evolved with computer-mediated communication (CMC). CMC has become the norm through the Internet, which Flammia and Saunders [1], described as a force for global unity. The Internet has given birth to e-language and transformed the English language. Brezina *et al.* [2] comparison of the British National Corpus 2014 (BNC2014) with the original British National Corpus 1994 (BNC1994) revealed that the Internet had changed the lexical and grammatical features of BrE. According to Brezina [3], BrE has become much more informal in blog posts, social media, and across genres, from fiction to newspapers, political speeches, and academic writing. For instance, the high frequency of informal features like contractions and second and first-person pronouns, which was unusual before the internet revolution, was revealed by the 2020 study. In addition, terms, acronyms, and spellings like *Alexa*, *app*, *awesome*, *blog*, *congrats*, *email*, *fab*, *Facebook*, *Fitbit*, *Instagram*, *iPad*, *iPhone*, *Ive*, *lol*, *omg*, *tbh*, *tweet*, *Twitter*, and *website* have become parts of e-language.

Ratih and Gusdian [4] analyzed the word-formation processes in English new words from 2012-2016 in the online Oxford English dictionary (OED) through systematic random sampling. They described the most common word-formation processes used on FB and identified the causes for employing these features. Their document analysis revealed that new English words are created through affixation, folk etymology, compounding, abbreviation, acronyms, borrowing, blending, clipping, and back-formation. They also found double word-formation processes: such as folk etymology and compounding, e.g., *historiosophy* from the Greek *historio* and *sophy*; compounding and affixation, e.g., *beatboxer* from *beat* and *box* and *er*; blending and affixation, e.g., *syntagmatic* from *syntax* and *pragmatic* and *s*; and clipping and blending, e.g., *d-line* from the *defensive line*.

In the Philippines, Facebook (FB) has become one of the most used social network sites where Filipinos communicate. Indeed, FB has become the most comfortable and fastest distance communication mode in the country. Tech in Asia records 94% of Filipino social media users through FB applications [5]. Adams [6] stated that FB is considered one of the most well-known social media sites; hence, many people around the globe get adopted to it regardless of whatever language is used. The FB posts and conversations between Filipino speakers of English are often scribed in Philippine English (henceforth PhilE), not the L₁ variety, BrE, or AmE; nevertheless, FB PhilE is underexplored.

Among the minimal studies on FB PhilE, include Afable *et al.* [7]. They looked at the process of creating new internet Philippine English (IPE) words and their acceptability to English as a second language (ESL) teachers through a corpus of about 300,000 words from “When in Manila” blogs from 2017-2019. Their analysis showed IPE lexical items formed through normal expansion, shortening, coinage, and borrowing based on Dimaculangan and Gustilo framework [8] of word-formation processes in PhilE. The items that emerged most frequently used were *x* (a shortened symbol that functions like *and*) and borrowed words from Tagalog like *adobo*, *hugot*, *balikbayan*, and *bongga*.

Gustilo *et al.* [9] measured the acceptability and intelligibility of IPE words and expressions in online news. They identified IPE lexical items in online showbiz news and determined the Filipino English ESL teachers' understanding of the words and their acceptance of these words in different domains of communication. Their 50,000-word corpus revealed 47 newly-formed IPE words that their ESL teacher participants generally understood; hence, they described the items as highly intelligible. Earlier than this study is Dino and Gustilo [10] exploration of the linguistic features of Filipino digitalk across FB, Instagram, Online Gaming, Twitter, Edmodo, and Blogs. They found 30 different linguistic features from a corpus of about 500 thousand words from the online interaction of 63 Filipino digitalkers. Among these 30 linguistic features are seven products of lexicon-building processes: acronyms, collocations, punning, affixation, borrowing, blending, and conversion.

Needless to say, social networking sites such as FB have changed man's linguistic environment; hence, FB English should be studied. As has been confirmed by the studies of Applied linguists and students [7], [9], [10], social networking sites can be a rich source of localized forms that can be added to the PhilE lexicon and contribute to the standardization of this variety of English. Therefore, the studies [7], [9], [10] suggested the conduct of studies on digitalk expressions and the proposal of a digitalk model to facilitate successful Internet communication and understanding among digitalkers. Moreover, prominent linguists recommended Internet language as a linguistic scholarship and material for thesis writing [11], [12].

The present study on the PhilE FB lexicon is significant not only because words are the building block of a language but also because FB seems to be the most favored mode of communication on the Internet and is now used as a platform for language learning. Moreover, FB PhilE, as an emerging variety of IPE, can be an addition to Gonzales [13] types of PhilE. The critical issue is a dearth of studies on FB PhilE, and research on FB PhilE is nascent. No one has comprehensively described the lexicon of FB PhilE. The past studies focused not on the lexicon of Internet chat but looked into the broader language variations in such a domain or determined the educated Filipino's attitude towards PhilE grammar and lexicon.

This study is relevantly timely, inasmuch as interlocutors across the globe engaged in online communication, mainly FB written communication; thus, they need to be updated about the lexicon development of various varieties for smooth and clear communication of messages across cultural boundaries. FB is now an ESL learning platform; hence, teaching FB language needs to be integrated with ELT instruction. FB PhilE vocabulary should also be taught when doing English vocabulary in Philippine ESL classrooms. This study offers a significant contribution to the limited literature on IPE, which is interesting to global ESL learners; they connect with the world through FB online communication using the hybridized Englishes understood by non-native speakers.

The paper aims to fill in the earlier mentioned gaps and offer practical implications for teaching ESL vocabulary by presenting common FB PhilE expressions and examining the word- mechanisms at work when they were formed. Specifically, it answers the questions: i) what FB PhilE words are found in ESL teachers' and students' FB posts and messages based on Bamgbose [14] and Sauza's frameworks [15]; and ii) what word-formation processes are evident in the lexical items based on Dimaculangan and Gustilo [8] proposed

framework? The present paper employed an innovative methodology called corpus linguistics. A corpus is a collection of examples of language in use that are selected and compiled in a principled way, and corpus linguistics is the linguistic study of such corpora [16]. In other words, it is the study of language through authentic naturally occurring language data produced by speakers or writers.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The study followed a descriptive research design and utilized qualitative-quantitative mixed methodologies. Scholars suggest that descriptive research is used to obtain information concerning the current status of phenomena to describe what exists concerning variables in a situation. It involves recording, describing, interpreting, and analyzing events and phenomena. This design was employed to describe the word-formation processes involved in creating FB PhilE vocabularies at the time of the study. A purely descriptive approach was observed in treating the FB PhilE lexes, i.e., the peculiarities and deviations were not corrected but merely described according to available evidence. Qualitative data were used to produce samples of commonly used PhilE lexical items found in the FB newsfeeds or timelines and conversations among ESL teachers and scholars and determine the word-formation processes in the identified lexical items.

2.2. Corpus and data collection procedures

The present paper utilized the corpus linguistics method in building the 50,000-word corpus of publicly posted messages in the ESL teachers' and students' FB newsfeeds and FB messenger conversations from which the lexical items were extracted. Qualitative data were used to obtain sample FB PhilE lexical items and to describe the lexical patterns inherent in the lexical formations. The data were collected through the self-built 50,000-word corpus of publicly posted messages in the FB newsfeeds or timelines and FB messenger conversations of educated users of PhilE (i.e., ESL teachers from primary to college/university levels across the country and college students from first to fourth years who are enrolled in the BSED-English program. The elementary and secondary school ESL teachers are Master's degree holders of Applied Linguistics or Education major in English or at least enrolled in any English Language Education programs.

The ESL scholars' permission for the researchers to use specific texts from their posts and conversations with the likers and reactors was first sought before data collection started in the last quarter of 2016. Therefore, only those texts from friends, colleagues, and classmates from all parts of the Philippines who granted permission were included in the study. These covered the texts that were posted from the last quarter of 2016 to 2022 by Filipino ESL teachers, graduate and undergraduate students 18 years old and over, and who had formal education in the country through the medium of English. These two parameters were adopted from the International corpus of English-Philippines [17] criteria in considering writers of the texts included in the corpus.

2.3. Data analysis procedures

The accessed posts and exchanges requested from the participants were manually collected, copied in Word, and set in plain text format. When the copying was completed and ready for analysis, it was fed into the WordSmith toolset to generate the wordlist of PhilE lexical items. The application presents all the words used in the analyzed texts, the frequencies of the terms that occurred, the percentage of the running words in the texts from which the wordlist was made, the number of texts that contained the specified words, and the percentage of the corpus of texts. In addition, the words and expressions were set out in alphabetical order through the alphabetical tab for easier identification of the target words.

The lexical items gathered were analyzed using Dimaculangan and Gustilo [8] proposed framework of word-formation processes used by Filipino speakers of English which was adopted from all the existing L1 English and ESL varieties' formation frameworks. Likewise, criteria were set to help the researchers identify PhilE neologisms from the list and their surrounding L1 English lexical items. The characterizing marks were based on [14] first two measures of ESL Englishes well-motivated innovations and D' Souza's, as cited in [15], first three criteria in standardizing usages in new Englishes.

The coinages were counted PhilE expressions when: i) they do not have L1 dictionary citations; ii) they are used by ESL teachers and students who are 18 years old and above and who had formal English instruction in the Philippines; iii) they are diffused by educated speakers from Luzon, Visayas, Mindanao, and National Capital Region (NCR); iv) they appear in the L1 English dictionary but are given new meanings; v) when the words are creatively coined and communicate meanings; and vi) they appeared in the gathered data at least five times. Dita (2015, personal communication) suggested the fifth criterion during one of the authors' oral defenses of her dissertation proposal on the early 20th-century PhilE lexicon.

After the groupings and classification, localized definitions of the items based on the contexts were determined. Repeated manual readings of the texts were done to provide appropriate contextual definitions. The lexical items whose semantic meanings were different from L₁ varieties' meanings were given American or British variety equivalents for clarity of the provided meanings. The words' congruity or incongruity with BrE and AmE varieties was checked against the current online version of Merriam-Webster's dictionary [18] and the online version of the OED [19]. Finally, quantitative statistics through frequency were also used to determine the productivity of the word-formation mechanisms involved.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Facebook PhilE lexicon per word-building mechanism

This section presents the data gathered from Facebook posts and conversations from the last quarter of 2016 to 2022. The answers to both the research questions, i.e., the lexical items and the word-formation processes, are presented together. The lexical items with a frequency of at least five are presented per word-formation process, from the most productive to the least productive. They are arranged alphabetically for easy reference; however, if two or more lexical items were found in a sentence or a paragraph, they are presented in a group and not as individual items for the readers' more explicit understanding of the word meanings.

3.1.1. Borrowing and hybridizing borrowed items with English markers

Researchers agree that lexical borrowing is widespread in the languages of the world, and it is a part of the word mechanism frameworks. Borrowing is a consequence of contact between two or more languages, and the PhilE language contact with Tagalog results in the borrowing of local terms. The data showed that PhilE FB communicants borrowed words from Tagalog into English posts and conversations, as can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of borrowed and hybridized Tagalog words with English plural markers

Lexical items	Meanings
(1) Bitin	(adj.) not sufficient; very short as in “ <i>Met my high school after ten years; had bitin one hour chat.</i> ”
(2) Chika/chikahan	(n.) stories; account of interlocutors' latest experience; light gossip/ the act of exchanging personal stories
(3) Din, pa, saka	(part.) discourse particles used as markers of addition; carry the semantic meaning of <i>and, too, or in addition to</i>
(4) Este	(part.) a colloquial particle that carries the phrasal meaning, <i>I mean...; I'm sorry, I mean...; I was to say...</i>
(5) Hurados	(n.) members of the panel of judges in skills and literary/musical competitions
(6) Kababayans	(n.) fellow Filipinos
(7) Lambing	(n.) sweetness
(8) Lanzonez, Mangosteen	(n.) Philippine tropical fruits
(9) Lola/lolo, apos	(n.) grandmother/grandfather, grandchildren
(10) Pinoys	(n. slang) Filipino citizens
(11) Po	Filipinos' discourse particle of respect
(12) Salubong dinner	(n.) welcome dinner
(13) Tatay	(n.) This Tagalog equivalent of father is used by wives as a vocative of endearment for their husbands and respect by the masses for the elderly.
(14) Kakamiss, nakakaproud	These two entries are clauses that express complete thoughts <i>I miss (something or someone).</i> The Tagalog prefix <i>kaka</i> , the short form of <i>nakaka</i> , expresses the state or tense of the action communicated by the verb <i>miss</i> and turns the adjective <i>proud</i> into a verb in the present form.
(15) Kita kits	It is the shortened form of <i>kita kita</i> , the Filipino expression, “ <i>see you.</i> ”
(16) Maraming salamat Salamat, Salamat kayo, Daghang salamat.	Thank you very much. Thank you

Borrowing is not a word-formation process; nevertheless, it is a way by which the vocabulary of a language grows [20]. The 21 lexical and grammatical items in lexical samples in Table 1 and another 15 infrequently used ones revealed the productivity of borrowing and code-switching Tagalog and English in the FB register. Indeed, data analysis revealed that the most productive word-building process in FB and FB Messenger conversations is borrowing from Philippine and foreign languages spoken in the country. This may be due to the informality of the domain, although FB communication is through the written medium. This finding jibes with Gustilo *et al.* [9] finding on the Filipinos' use of informal and borrowed items in Internet English. Further, the present data show the FB communicants' borrowing of Tagalog expressions and morphologically treating them as English lexicon, as shown by the samples numbered 5, 6, 9, and 10.

Borrowing from local languages, compounding English and borrowed words as in Item no. 7, and affixing Tagalog words with English particles localize FB PhilE.

PhilE borrowing from Philippine languages confirms Kirkpatrick [21] proposition that varieties of English adapt words that suit the culture in which they are used. The data proved his conviction that a variety of English will not survive without words that reflect cultures and contexts. The codemixed posts (e.g., *Before this day ends, I would like to greet my two inaanaks, a happy birthday; Happy birthday pards and mars; and # The gorgeous hurados*) implicitly reflect the colorful culture of the Filipinos. Most of the borrowed expressions support Salazar [22] observation that English in the Philippines, as in many parts of the world, is continually changing, and its distinctive vocabulary reflects the colorful culture and history of the Filipinos.

3.1.2. Forming initialisms

Shortened words are treated as new words, increasing the vocabulary of a language. Another way by which new PhilE lexical items are born is through clipping and initialism, i.e., abbreviation and acronym [23]. Utilizing their initialism model incorporated in the PhilE word-formation processes proposed model [8], the following abbreviations and acronyms are identified in Table 2.

Table 2. Sample initials used in Facebook posts

Tagalog sounding acronyms	Meaning
(1) ARAL	Action Research Action Learning <i>Aral</i> is the Tagalog equivalent of the English study; however, in this paper, it is an acronym formed from the given spelled-out meaning.
(2) LIDER	Lasallian Institute for Development and Education <i>Lider</i> is the Tagalog form of the English <i>leader</i>
(3) MOOCers	Teachers and students who engage themselves in the Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) from American universities offered through the Regional English Language Office (RELO) under the Public Affairs Section of the US Embassy in Manila.
(4) PNUans, LUans	Philippine Normal University alumni; Laguna University alumni
(5) STIers	Faculty and students of the Systems Technology Institute (STI)

Worthy of attention is the FB users' way of shortening words and phrases by forming initials, i.e., non-English sounding acronyms and agentive acronyms and abbreviations, as shown in Table 2. Lexicologists and linguists [23], [24], use the term *initialism* to cover abbreviations and acronyms, which are used interchangeably by some scholars but differentiated by others. An abbreviation consists of the initial letters of a phrase that is read letter by letter; thus, a study [24] calls it an *alphabetic abbreviation*. An acronym also consists of initial letters of multiple lexemes; however, the output is pronounced as a word.

Filipino Facebookers also use common abbreviations like ATM for *at this moment*, FYI for *for your information*, GM for *Group message*, HB for *Happy birthday*, LOL for *Laugh out loud*, MBTC for *More birthdays to come*, and PM for *Personal Message* which is used as a noun or a verb. However, they are also common abbreviations in other Englishes; thus, they are no longer enumerated in the table, although they are also part of the FB PhilE lexicon. PhilE lexicon consists of expressions that developed locally and are thus distinctively PhilE, and expressions that developed elsewhere, which have spread throughout the English-speaking countries, not just in the Philippines. No sample of Asbah [25] pseudo-acronyms (i.e., initials) that, when pronounced, resemble the sounds of intended words, e.g., ICQ from *I seek you* and IOU from *I owe you* were found in the corpus.

The Filipinos seem familiar with this type of word formation; they unconsciously form abbreviations and acronyms from the names of buildings around them, their university offices, designations (e.g., CD from Campus Director), and titles of television shows. FB PhilE users also extend the process of initialism by coining Tagalog-sounding acronyms, items 1 and 2, with English, spelled out expansions. The same Tagalog acronyms were in the analysis of linguistically acceptable neologisms in early 21st-century PhilE writing [26]. The data also reflect the FB communicants personifying abbreviation and acronym through the agentive suffix *er*, as shown by samples 3 and 5. Further, the acronym MOOC is verbalized by conversion or affixation as in MOOC/MOOCing to mean, do/doing the massive open online courses, e.g., *MOOCing forward; Let's MOOC a difference*.

3.1.3. Clipped forms/clipping

Clipping is reducing a longer word into a shorter one without changing its meaning. The well-cited linguist [27], [28] explained that when a word of more than one syllable is reduced to a shorter form, it becomes a new word from the process. Plag [29] calls it truncation, while others call it shortening. The succeeding table presents the list of clipped forms used more than five times in the present database.

Another way new FB PhilE lexical items are born is by shortening existing words through clipping. The clipped items in Table 3 that repeatedly appeared in the data are informal yet catchy, and they make the communication of the messages lively. Although limited, they show FB users' flexibility in adapting to language change. Items 1, 3, and 8, which were not productively used, illustrate Yule [27], [28] hypocoristic clipping, i.e., the original noun forms are truncated into one-syllable lexical items and then added the syllable, i.e., or y. This morphological change appears to communicate the closeness and festive mood of the FB communicants. *Pix* for picture or photo, *sesh* for session, *xperience* or *xpi* for experience, and *accre* for accreditation were among the clipped forms used more than once. *Sesh* in *Karaoke sesh*, which means *session*, is another impressive clipped form due to the addition of the (sh)sound. However, the informality and colloquialism of these clipped forms may cause their short life span.

Table 3. Clipped forms

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Aftie	(n.) afternoon
(2) Bora	(n.) Boracay Island, which is famous for its beaches
(3) Breaky, brekki	(n.) breakfast
(4) Celebs	(n.) celebration Celeb is AmE and BriE's clipped form of <i>celebrity</i> .
(5) Cong	(n.) congressman The L ₁ English <i>cong</i> is the abbreviation of <i>congress</i> and <i>congressional</i> .
(6) Sissy/sissies	(v.) the singular and non-singular forms of sister BrE noun <i>sissy</i> (or <i>sissiness</i>) is derogatory referring to a soft and over sensitive person or a man seen as interested in things associated with women; as an adjective, it has the comparative and superlative <i>sissier</i> and <i>sissiest</i> forms. It is a derogatory noun in AmE's referring to a weak or cowardly person, aside from effeminate man which also sounds BrE.
(7) Resto	(n.) restaurant Resto has no citation in Webster's but cited in Oxford Dictionary carrying the same meaning, short form of restaurant.
(8) Tricy	(n.) tricycle, motorcycle attached to a passenger cab that is a common means of transportation in rural areas. The truncated form <i>tricy</i> has no citation in both Webster's and Oxford Dictionaries.

3.1.4. Orthographic deviations/respelling

Another interesting composition of PhilE vocabularies found in FB posts and conversations are graphologically deviant or playfully spelled items to indirectly communicate intimacy, fun, or creativity in written language. The corpus also showed English lexical items spelled in Filipino for localization impact. Among these lexical items that appeared five times or more in the corpus are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Sample respelled words and expressions

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Bebegurl	(n.) baby girl, daughter
(2) Ferson	(n.) a person who stands out or in the spotlight
(3) Freny	(n.) a friend
(4) Fudhaus/hauz	(n.) a small eatery It is the pronunciation-based spelling of food-house, a PhilE endocentric compound.
(5) Fudtrip	(n.) food trip, a coined Filipino English exocentric compound. The one-word text post is defined by the pictures of a salivating meal or food the digitalker would satisfy his gastronomic desire.
(6) Luv yeah, luv u, labyu	(clause) I love you
(7) Mamsh, mamshie, popsky/popsie	(n.) colloquial light terms for mama and papa (mother and father)
(8) Tenk u, thnx, tenchu	(clause) Thank you
(9) forda dokyu...	(phrase) The expression is the cool way of the English <i>for the docu</i> (documentation) team

The educated FB PhilE users' playfulness and creativity in changing L1 English words' orthographic structures or giving them Tagalog spelling is a part of the frameworks used for this study. Table 4 presents nine colloquial expressions used at least five times by digitalkers. In addition to the items, which carry original L1 semantic meanings, are two simple sentences that are transformed into deviant one-word items that still communicate the complete sentences' original meanings: *lezzgo* from *Let's go* and *mishu* from *I miss you*/ *miss you*. The new spelling reflects the exaggerated pronunciation of the items, which gave the messages a more personal festive tone.

Apart from the frequently used expressions, three slang appeared four times and once, respectively. *Gurlash* or *gurl*, slang for girl, however, refers to a lady or woman friend appeared four times in the corpus;

whereas *mudrakeli* sounds like a gay jargon yet was used by an ESL teacher to refer to a mother appeared once in the corpus. In addition, the spelling calques and instances of pronunciation spelling do not just emphasize the words' correct pronunciation but also inject humor required by the contexts. They silently communicate the FB Filipino society's lightheartedness and intimacy; for instance, *bebegurl* and *tenchu* are terms of endearment and love among families and close friends.

3.1.5. Compounds/compounding

A compound is a combination of two or more closely related words that produces a new meaning. It may be written as two words, as a single word, or as two or more words separated by a hyphen. Lexicologists like [30]–[32] suggest three kinds of compounds: the endocentric compound, which has a transparent meaning carried by the head; the exocentric compound with an unexpressed semantic head, hence idiomatic; the synthetic compound which involves compounding and derivation; and the neoclassical compound which is a mixture of classical and English elements.

Word-formation theorists qualify a compound as a combination of two or more stems that form a potential new stem. In this case, one of the components can modify the other noun. The data did not reveal academic or formal compounds; the interesting compounds seen in Table 5 are limited to informal endocentric and exocentric, with code-mixed English and English Tagalog compounds. Items 5-8 are light-sounding code-switched compounds made up of Tagalog words blended with the superlative degree of the adjunct *many* and are all graphologically written as one-word compounds. World Englishes authorities [25], [33] found compounding to be a productive word-formation process and asserted that it had been a constant feature of PhilE vocabulary; however, the present data show a different trend in online speech. Nevertheless, it can be noted that there are compounds in other parts that are included under other processes, e.g., the pun *vitaminsea* (vitamin C) is a compound.

Table 5. Compounds

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Bornday	(n.) variation of birthday
(2) Classhome	(n.) a classroom that radiates a home ambiance
(3) Sunkissed	(adj.) lightly bitten by sunlight; directly exposed to the sun
Tagalog English compounds	
(5) Busogmuch	(adj.) full and satisfied with the meal,
(6) Gulatmuch	caught unaware or surprised
(7) Pagodmuch	(adj.) very tired
(8) Happylang	(adj.) I am/we are happy. It is an expression that is scribed with a photo showing the participants' satisfaction with an activity or achievement.
(9) Tawamuch	(v.) to keep laughing due to so much fun

3.1.6. Punned lexes/punning

The corpus also revealed coinages that illustrate the FB messengers' intentional punning. Nordquist [34] qualifies a pun as a figure of speech in wordplay that deliberately exploits ambiguity between similar-sounding words for humorous or rhetorical effect. Other scholars on figurative language state that the play is on similar sounds and sometimes on slightly changed or completely different meanings. The play on words is done to produce more than one meaning from the same words or expressions. The following puns appear repeatedly in the corpus.

Although Table 6 reflects only 10 instances of repeated puns, the ELT teachers' punning cannot be disregarded. These delightful puns illustrated their intelligent play with words to communicate specific meanings. The coined fancy words and the word choices fit the contexts in which they were used quite rightly so that readers could effortlessly infer what the puns mean. Punning seemed to be done not only to inject humor but to enliven the thoughts and make the communication of meanings a little thought-provoking. The samples reflect the punsters' knowledge of homonyms, good sense of diction, and brilliance in playing with words for intended effects and contextual meanings. Unsurprisingly, ESL punsters know the right words to create at the right time and place.

A pun that appeared less than five times in the corpus is *actista* from the acronym advanced computer training school (ACTS), which is blended with the truncated form of the Tagalog *artista* (movie actor) to describe the male punster as one good-looking movie actor. Another is *mush* from *Thank you very mush; yummy*, after she was sent mushroom crackling. The syllable *mush* from the mushroom is deliberately punned with the slightly rhyming *much*.

Table 6. Punned expressions

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Congradulations	(interj.) Congratulations on your graduation. It is the blend of the first syllable of the interjection, congratulations, and the word <i>graduation</i> ; the phoneme <i>t</i> in congratulations is omitted, after which the first syllable of the noun <i>graduation</i> is inserted.
(2) Fridate, saturdate, sundate, holidate, yesterdate	(n.) lovers' or friends' date on a specific day, a meeting for bonding and pleasure. The morpheme <i>date</i> seems to be forcefully made to rhyme with the end syllable of the days of the week.
(3) Gradwaiting	(n.) a student who has completed the academic requirements and is waiting for graduation rites
(4) Habeerday	(Clause) Happy birthday; it is a birthday greeting containing a jokey invitation for social drinking, specifically beer
(5) Seasid	(verbal) spending the day in the sea or enjoying the waters The noun <i>sea</i> is converted into a verb and punned with <i>seized</i> .
(6) Pawty	(n., v.) a dog's birthday, celebrate a dog's birthday. This coinage is from the dog's <i>paw</i> and the final syllable of <i>party</i> .
(7) Tues (to love/tobehappy)	(v.) decide to be in love and happy on a Tuesday The punning is on the near similar sounds of <i>choose</i> and <i>Tues</i> .
(8) Vitaminsea	(n.) the natural physical and emotional nourishment one gets from the sea breeze or sunlight when going swimming or sunbathing in the sea The compound is created by punning the sound C in <i>Vitamin C</i> and <i>sea</i> in the new coinage.
(8) Wabyu	(Clause) I love you

3.1.7. Derivation/affixation

Another word-formation mechanism found in the present data is derivation, which is also termed affixation and suffixation [35] or adding of derivational affixes [22]. It is a major type of morphological operation that forms new words by adding derivational affixes to stems. Derivational affixes change the functions and meanings of words as opposed to inflectional affixes that show the formation of grammatical variants only.

FB PhilE vocabularies is also enriched by the derivation, which, according to previous studies [27], [28], is the most common word-formation process in the production of new English words. Table 7 on derivation shows the ESL scholars' deliberate forming of familiar-sounding *able* adjectives, items 3, 4, and 7, and a noun, item 1. Other interesting derivations which did not reach the paper frequency requirement to be considered lexicon of FB were: i) the exaggerated superlative form of best, *bestest*; ii) the conversion of the nominal *life* to the adjective in the comparative degree *lifer*; and iii) the deliberate overgeneralization of pluralizing *guy* to *guyses* for impact and humor. The coiners knew that they were playing with word formation, as suggested by the laughing emoticons attached to the text. Further, data show three instances of verbing the nouns *memorandum* and *revolution* into *memorandize* and *revolutionalize*.

Table 7. Derivations

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Checkables	(n.) students' short tests, which are for teachers' feedback
(2) Dean's lister	(n.) dean's list The <i>lister</i> in dean's lister is probably formed in analogy with <i>er</i> -ending nouns.
(3) Googleable	(adj.) something that can be found or explained by the Google search engine
(4) Instagrammable	(adj.) photo or video can be displayed on one's Instagram profile.
(5) Masteral	(n.) a master's degree It is an old PhilE word that is analogically constructed with <i>al</i> adjectives
(6) Monthsary, weeksary	(n.) weekly or monthly celebration or anniversary of a special or an important event
(7) Throwbackable	(adj.) memorable

3.1.8. Blending

Blending is another feature of FB PhilE; is coining clipped elements into one new lexical item. As advanced by the German linguist [36], it is a modern type of word formation. The theorist [30], proposes that most blends are formed by: i) adding the beginning of one word to the end of another; ii) combining the beginnings of two words; iii) blending two words' typical sequence of sounds; and iv) blending multiple sounds of two-component words.

As can be gleaned in Table 8, three commonly used blends are made up of words that are clipped simultaneously: *fambam*, *condotel*, *famvacay*. Four more blends: *churchfam* from church family referring to brethren, *enjoycational* from enjoyable and educational, and *shortcation* from short vacation, which show

unclipped initial constituents appeared in the corpus. One exciting item *stratplan* which appeared in the 2019 corpus is a blend of the truncated form of *strategic planning*. One Taglish blend, *salamuch*, which has high frequency, is made up of the first two syllables of the Tagalog expression of gratitude, (*sala*)*mat*, and the English adverb, *much*. The coinage is also punned with *salamat* since the final syllable (*mat*) slightly rhymes with the adverb *much*.

Table 8. Words from blending

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Condotel	(n.) a transient, cozy room of a <i>condominium</i> that appears like a <i>hotel</i> room
(2) Fambam	(n.) <i>family bonding</i>
(3) Famvacay	(n.) <i>family vacation</i>
(4) Friendversary	(n.) anniversary of <i>friendship</i>
(5) Edukcircle	(n.) a group of educators, teachers, scholars, and students sharing the same interest; This form is blended from the back-clipped form of <i>Edukasyon</i> , the Tagalog word for education, <i>Eduk</i> , and the English word <i>circle</i> .

3.1.9. Vocal segregates

Vocal segregates, i.e., common filler sounds such as: *uh-uh-uh*, *er*, and *ah*, which are inherent in oral speech, are adopted in printed FB PhilE. FB conversant appears to be natural, conversational, and comfortable with PhilE; thus, they use the informal register to express emotions and give them orthographic representations as shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Spelled out vocal segregates

Verbalized vocal segregates	Meaning
(1) Ha ha ha/hu hu hu	Orthographic representation of a man's laughs and cry
(2) Mwahh	Perceived sound of an electronic kiss
(3) Tsk tsk tsk	A paralinguistic unit communicating a feeling of regret over someone or something that could have been well done or treated
(4) Zzzz	State of sleeping

The corpus also revealed repeated use of vocal segregates in FB Messenger conversations, such as the items grouped in Table 9. The items have recorded very high frequency since 2016. These onomatopoeic words have predictable meanings based on the combinations of sounds that make them up. They reflect clear meaning to the social media users; however, without the context, the meanings of items 2 and 3 may be unpredictable to those not familiar with communication technology. The verbalization of these fillers on the FB platform may be due to the informal nature of FB communication and the emotional nature of Filipinos.

3.1.10. Semantic shift

The proponents [8] of the proposed word-formation processes framework for 21st Century PhilE Lexicon also cover the semantic shift, which is the summary of Gramley [35] discussion of semantic broadening (i.e., extension of meaning) and narrowing. Gramley [35] has both denotative widening and narrowing and connotation, that covers *amelioration* when a word adopts a positive connotation and *pejoration* when it takes a derogatory meaning.

As shown in Table 10, the present data reflected four instances of semantic shift, the contextual and denotative meanings provided. In the text message, *please send me your OPCR asap; I will consolidate our data and send it back to you* with the reply, *Copied po ma'am* (Yes, ma'am/I understand, ma'am) with the inserted *po*, the Tagalog particle of respect, the word *copied* communicates the specified meaning. The semantic shifting in Item 2 might have been brought about by repeated similar communications that registered such local denotations in the users' mental lexicon. The Filipinos' reception of the telecommunication networks' and fast-food chains' advertisements and promotions, tagged with the expression *unlimited* (e.g., unlimited rice, unlimited drinks, and unlimited texting), registered the definitions in their mental lexicon.

Table 10. Words given additional or new meanings

Lexical items	Meaning
(1) Gets, copied	(adj.) message understood
(2) Unlimited/unli	(adj.) specific measures or restrictions; duration or extension of networks' services The denotation of the word <i>unlimited</i> , which is <i>no bounds or limits</i> , is narrowed into i) <i>specific measures or restrictions</i> and ii) <i>duration or extension of networks' services</i> . For instance, the free calls and text messages can be done in two days, one week, or one month and expire after that.
(3) Educators	(n.) BriE teachers AmE English meaning covers the students of the theory and practice of education, teachers, and administrators in education.
(4) Groupie	(adj.) to be or come in a group; (v) take a group photo Webster's <i>groupie</i> singularly refers to a <i>fan of a rock group</i> who follows the group around at a concert or <i>an enthusiastic supporter of a celebrity or something</i> . The word <i>groupie</i> , which is given a new semantic meaning, is not a case of amelioration or pejoration but merely a new meaning.

3.1.11. Anagrammatic transposition

An anagram is a word or expression from rearranged letters of another word. Oxford dictionary defines it as a word or phrase made by transposing the letters of another word or phrase, as in *dusty* from *study*. The four interesting anagrams were found frequently used in PhilE FB communication.

Table 11 presents five instances of anagrammatic transposition or backward spelling, that are not part of the proposed Dimaculangan and Gustilo framework [8], were used; thus, although they are limited, they are presented due to the Face bookers' repeated use. The first three items are also familiar expressions in English or Tagalog informal conversations. The inverted and backwardly spelled words retained the same semantic meanings and confirmed the personal and informal tone of FB PhilE.

Table 11. Anagrammatic transposition

Transformed lexical items	Original form
Lodi	Idol
typar	party
werpo (Read as werpa)	power
SsimNly	Miss Lyn
Zurcaled	Dela Cruz

3.1.12. Hypocoristic extension

The present researchers borrow a Yule [27] hypocoristic clipping; however, they change clipping into (*hypocoristic*) *extension*. Yule [28] hypocoristic clipping called hypocorism is the reduction of a long word or expression into a single syllable word and the addition of y or, i.e., to its end (e.g., moving pictures to movie and handkerchief to hankie). The present paper's *hypocoristic extension* extends a short word into a two-syllable word by adding the, i.e., final morpheme.

The four splashy items as shown in Table 12, marked by the addition of the, i.e., or y final syllable, become more eye-catching not only because they are formed by doubling the syllable of their original L1 English forms through the suffix, i.e., or y, but also because this Philippine word-building process seems the opposite of Yule [27], [28] hypocoristic clipping. Like hypocoristically clipped forms. They reflect the FB dialog participants' closeness, jolliness, and lightheartedness.

Table 12. Hypocoristic extension

Lexical items	Meaning
1) Besty	(n. informal) variation of <i>best friend</i> The modifier <i>best</i> is nouned by adding <i>y</i> and carries the meaning of <i>best friend</i> . The form appears in the Longman dictionary of contemporary English but not in the OED and Merriam-Webster's dictionary.
2) Hottie	(adj.) hot, humid weather It is an L1 English word referring to a physically attractive person.
3) Thankie	Thank you. It is probably formed in analogy with the L1 English, <i>Thankee</i> [37], which is an interjection used to express gratitude
4) Twinnie	Twin L1 English <i>weeny</i> [38] or <i>weenie</i> is a <i>betweenmaid</i> , i.e., a <i>maidservant</i> whose work supplements that of cook and housemaid

3.1.13. Shift in part of speech

The proposed word-formation processes framework for 21st century PhilE lexicon [8] includes Normal Expansion, which was borrowed from Bautista as cited in [20]. Bautista's paradigm of normal expansion involves two processes: i) *extension or adaptation of meaning*; and ii) *shift in a part of speech*, which involves: i) sub-categorization of a specific part of speech; and ii) unidiomatic verb preposition combination. The shift may or may not be zero conversion but conversion through suffixation (e.g., the noun traffic to adj. traffic and the noun fiscal to the verb fiscalize).

Limited expressions were found for the category *shift in part of speech*, as shown in Table 13. One reason might be the classification of some whose shift from one lexical category to another involved affixation; hence, they were classified as words created by derivation. These minimal expressions that display change in word class or subcategories of the word classes may also convey the FB PhilE community's advancement from being norm dependents to being norm providers. Relatively, PhilE reality counts, as far as the OED and the English language are concerned; thus, Filipinos should celebrate PhilE linguistic evolution as suggested by Sampayan [39].

Table 13. Shift in part of speech

Expressions	Meaning
1) Breakfasting	It involves verbing the noun breakfast to mean <i>having breakfast</i> .
2) God bless!	The L1 English transitive verb <i>bless</i> is used as an intransitive verb in this leave-taking part of a conversion.
3) Enjoy!	It is also a clause that expresses a complete thought in which the transitive verb <i>enjoy</i> in <i>Enjoy yourself</i> is used as an intransitive verb.
4) Researches	The noun countable L1 <i>research</i> is treated as a countable noun and pluralized by adding the plural countable marker <i>es</i> . Other Englishes use the plural form, <i>researches</i> , but grammarians say it is rare and uncommon.

3.2. Facebook PhilE lexicon frequencies

For a quicker look at the processes found in the last quarter of 2016 to 2022 FB PhilE expressions, this section is concluded with Table 14, which summarizes the preceding discussion. The processes with their frequencies are presented from highest to lowest. The summary excluded the terms that were not repeatedly used, i.e., those that appeared to have a short life span.

Table 14. Summary of FB PhilE lexicon frequencies

	Formation mechanisms	Frequencies
(1)	Borrowing and hybridizing borrowed words with English Suffixes	31
(2)	Forming initialism	14
(3)	Orthographic deviation/respelling	12
	Derivation	12
(4)	Blending	11
	Punning	11
(5)	Compounding	9
(6)	Clipping	8
	Spelling out vocal Segregates	4
	Semantic shifting	4
	Shift in part of speech	4
(7)	Hypocoristic extension	4
(8)	Anagrammatic transposition/backward spelling	4

Examination of the 117 lexical items in Table 14 shows that they are products of the FB interlocutors' knowledge of rule-governed English word-formation processes and skillful linguistic creativity, which Dimaculangan and Gustilo [8] summarize. FB PhilE is formed through the existing standard L₁ and ESL word-building processes, such as the 1-6 mechanisms shown in Table 14. Interestingly, two additional creative processes were found and numbered 7 and 8 processes, which are the present authors' contributions to the proposed [8] framework. They are i) hypocoristic extension, the opposite of [27], [28] hypocoristic clipping, and ii) anagrammatic transposition or what other scholars call backward spelling. The German word-formation scholar [36] suggests that new words may not be all products of established morphological rules but of rule-bending creativity, too.

Table 14 reveals, too, that borrowing and affixing borrowed lexemes with English particles and treating them as English vocabularies were the most common ways the participants increased the lexicon of FB PhilE. It seems that FB PhilE borrows words more than creates new ones. Coining particular types of initialisms and clipping are the second and third productive processes in producing words for online

communication. The other processes are not far behind. The last four creative formations are equally unique; nonetheless, the small frequency may suggest the words' short life span. In sum, the wordlist confirms that the lexicon-building processes in FB PhilE include the ones proposed by [8] with the addition of the present paper's *hypocoristic extension* and *anagrammatic transposition or backward spelling*. ESL learners need to be exposed to actual language in diverse linguistic and social contexts because authentic discourse makes the language easier to comprehend and makes learning easy and enjoyable. PhilE FB lexicology must be taught to Filipino students; the use of the FB lexicon allows PhilE speakers of the language to understand and shape the language according to their communicative needs. The expressions that are intelligible to other speakers of English should be taught, while those that may cause unintelligibility in lingua franca communication may be discarded. In this era, when English is the lingua franca of the multilingual world, teaching FB PhilE lexicon may facilitate the intelligibility of the written PhilE and promote smooth communication among World Englishes FB interlocutors.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study shows that Facebook English resembles spoken English due to the use of a colloquial lexicon. The conversational style brought by the everyday lexical items seems to indicate the participants' membership to the social group of educated L₁ and L₂ Englishes speakers, the prescriptive grammarians inside the classrooms, but celebrators of language growth and change outside the classrooms. The gathered data suggest that Filipino ESL teachers and students are reshaping and coloring FB PhilE lexicon through their innate and playful linguistic knowledge and flexibility, which they consciously display in the widely used media platform where interlocutors use authentic language. They handily and creatively coin words to communicate life's events, statuses, and announcements in engaging and exciting ways. The modes of word development appear appealing because they reflect the ELT practitioners' deliberate non-adherence to the prescriptive word-formation rules and their bubbly openness to rule-bending word-coining mechanisms; hence, they have produced stylistic linguistic items.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Laguna State Polytechnic University President Dr. Mario R. Briones for continually recognizing, motivating, and encouraging the University officials with all the faculty members to improve the management system as well as pedagogy through research. Their gratitude also goes to the Vice Presidents for Academic Affairs, Research and Development, and Administration: Dr. Eden C. Callo, Prof. Roberto Agatep, and Engr. Pedrigal, respectively, for the constant support to this academic endeavor.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Flammia and C. Saunders, "Language as power on the Internet," *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, vol. 58, no. 12, pp. 1899–1903, Oct. 2007, doi: 10.1002/asi.20659.
- [2] V. Brezina, A. Hawtin, and T. McEnery, "The written British National Corpus 2014—design and comparability," *Text & Talk*, vol. 41, no. 5–6, pp. 595–615, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1515/text-2020-0052.
- [3] V. Brezina, "Five ways the internet era has changed British English—new research." *The Conversation*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://theconversation.com/five-ways-the-internet-era-has-changed-british-english-new-research-172432>.
- [4] E. Ratih and R. I. Gusdian, "Word formation processes in English new words of Oxford English dictionary (OED) online," *Celtic: A Journal of Culture, English Language Teaching, Literature and Linguistics*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 24–35, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.22219/celtic.v5i2.7617.
- [5] A. Sweeney, "Philippines mobile internet trends: young, affluent, and growing fast," *On device research*, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://ondeviceresearch.com/blog/philippines-mobile-internet-trends> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).
- [6] D. Adams, "Understanding the Impact of Internet on Language," *CCJK*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ccjk.com/impact-of-internet-on-language/> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).
- [7] C. B. Afable, H. N. M. Austria, and J. D. Evidente, "Lexical features of when in manila blogs: IPE word-formation processes and their acceptability to ESL teachers," *Modern Journal of Studies in English Language Teaching and Literature*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 50–67, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.56498/31202149.
- [8] N. G. Dimaculangan and L. E. Gustilo, "A closer look at Philippine English word-formation frameworks," *Advanced Science Letters*, vol. 24, no. 11, pp. 8384–8388, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1166/asl.2018.12569.
- [9] L. Gustilo, A. W. I. Tocalo, and K. A. Calingasan, "The intelligibility and acceptability of Internet Philippine English (IPE): Their implications to English language teaching in the new English varieties," *Asian EFL Journal*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 83–104, 2019.
- [10] C. M. Dino and L. Gustilo, "FB digitalking: Standard, non-standard, or hybrid?" *Advanced Science Letters*, vol. 24, no. 11, pp. 8328–8331, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1166/asl.2018.12554.
- [11] D. Crystal, *Into the twenty-first century. Language and the Internet*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- [12] G. Ranger, "David crystal, language and the internet," *Lexis*, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.4000/lexis.1831.
- [13] W. D. W. Gonzales, "Philippine Englishes," *Asian Englishes*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 79–95, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1080/13488678.2016.1274574.
- [14] A. Bamgbose, "Torn between the norms: innovations in world Englishes," *World Englishes*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Mar. 1998, doi: 10.1111/1467-971X.00078.
- [15] M. Lourdes and M. L. S. Bautista, *Defining standard Philippine English: Its status and grammatical features*. Publisher: De La Salle University Press, 2000.

- [16] C.-R. Huang and Y. Yao, "Corpus linguistics," in *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, Elsevier, 2015, pp. 949–953, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.52004-2.
- [17] International Corpus of English (ICE)-Philippines, "Design of ICE corpora." International Corpus of English, Universität Zürich. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ice-corpora.uzh.ch/en/Joinice/Teams/icephi.html> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).
- [18] "Gas Definition," Online Merriam Webster's dictionary. [Online]. Available: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/gas>
- [19] "Oxford English dictionaries." Oxford University Press. [Online]. Available: <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/>
- [20] N. Dimaculangan, "Formation processes and teachers' attitude on Philippine English lexicon," Ph.D. Dissertation, De La Salle University Manila, Philippines, 2016.
- [21] A. Kirkpatrick, "English as an Asian lingua franca and the multilingual model of ELT," *Language Teaching*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 212–224, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1017/S0261444810000145.
- [22] D. Salazar, "What is the OED and why do we want Philippine English to be in it?" 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://pinoywords.wordpress.com> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).
- [23] R. Huddleston and G. K. Pullum, *The Cambridge grammar of the English language*. Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [24] V. Fromkin, R. Rodman, and N. N. Hyams, "Morphological change," *Introduction to Linguistics*, pp. 446–459, 2011.
- [25] A. Asbah, "Word formation in Facebook conversation; a study at a group Prodi English Department FKIP University Muhammadiyah of Mataram in academic year 2015-2016," *Linguistics and ELT Journal*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 29–36, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.31764/eltj.v10i2.792.
- [26] N. G. Dimaculangan and L. E. Gustilo, "Lexical patterns in the early 21st-century Philippine English writing," *Advanced Science Letters*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1094–1098, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1166/asl.2017.7505.
- [27] G. Yule, *The study of language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- [28] G. Yule, *The study of language*. 4th Ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [29] I. Plag, *Word-formation in English*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [30] T. Biermeier, "Lexical trends in Philippine English," in *Studies of Philippine English: Exploring the Philippine component of the International Corpus of English*, M.L.S. Bautista, Ed., 2011, pp. 223–247.
- [31] R. Wardhaugh, *Understanding English Grammar: A linguistic approach*. Second edition. Blackwell Publishing, 2003.
- [32] R. Lieber, *Morphology and lexical semantics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- [33] K. Bolton and S. Butler, "Lexicography and the description of Philippine English vocabulary," in *Philippine English*, Hong Kong University Press, 2008, pp. 175–195, doi: 10.5790/hongkong/9789622099470.003.0010.
- [34] R. Nordquist, "Top 20 Figures of speech," *ThoughtCo.*, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://grammar.about.com/od/rhetoricstyle/a/20figures.htm> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).
- [35] S. Gramley, *The vocabulary of world English*. London, Arnold, 2001.
- [36] T. Biermeier, *Word-formation in new Englishes: A corpus-based analysis*. Lit Verlag, 2008.
- [37] "Thankee Definition." Online Merriam Webster's dictionary. [Online]. Available: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/thankee>
- [38] "Betweenmaid Definition." Online Merriam Webster's dictionary. [Online]. Available: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/betweenmaid>
- [39] J. T. Sampayan, "What is Philippine English, and why should pinoyos stop looking down on it?" 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://news.abs-cbn.com/ancx/culture/spotlight/08/22/20/what-is-philippine-english-and-why-should-pinoyos-stop-looking-down-on-it> (accessed Jan. 14, 2023).

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nimfa G. Dimaculangan is the current Director for International and Local Affairs at Laguna State Polytechnic University. She is a faculty member, Full Professor of the College of Teacher Education, teaching Language-related courses and Research. Apart from teaching, she also serves as an international and local research journals reviewer, thesis/dissertation editor, external research evaluator, and resource speaker on Research, Language, and Language Teaching related topics. She has presented papers in Asian countries, the USA, and London (virtual) and has published in Scopus and ISI-indexed journals. She can be contacted at email: nimfadimaculangan@lspu.edu.ph.

Michelle B. Sarmiento is an Associate Professor II at the Laguna State Polytechnic University (LSPU), concurrently handling strategic administrative and leadership functions such as being the Executive Assistant to the LSPU President, Managing Editor of the Presidential Media Affairs Office, and Interim LSPU Board Secretary. She is also the adviser of the Federated Supreme Student Council of LSPU. She was also the former Director of the Office of Student Affairs from AY 2020-2021. She can be contacted at email: michelle.sarmiento@lspu.edu.ph.